

Deformation Mechanism Investigation for Epoxy by In-situ Electrical and Mechanics Coupling Measurement

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Materials and specimen

Epoxy-matrix composite with 0.0 and 3.0 wt.% of CNT, cylindrical specimen: $\varnothing 4.0 \text{ mm} \times 4.0 \text{ mm}$.

Electro-mech coupling measurement and its behaviors

Figure 1 Schematic map of specimen resistance measurement (A), and the experimental picture of compression test where the glass pads are used for shielding potential interference (B).

Figure 2 Origin experimental data of CNT composite under compressive loading: (A) load-displacement curve and (B) the corresponding specimen voltage signal, and calculated stress-strain curve and volume resistivity curve during deforming.

Mechanical measurement and results

Figure 3 Stress-strain curves of epoxy under different strains (A) with the previous three experiments below peak stress, and (B) with the previous nine experiments over peak stress.

where E_1 is the elastic modulus of the first load for each specimen involved, and E_{si} was the specific elastic modulus of the i th load, with $i=2,3$, until to 10.

Figure 4 Specific elastic modulus comparisons for prior to, beyond peak stress.

The mechanism proposed

Figure 5 Deformation and microstructure evolution process of nanocomposite.

The mechanism is predicted for the matrix epoxy of nanocomposite that the cross-linked sites are about to break when the specimen is loaded to peak stress, and the more molecular chain units freed from the broken sites can form the molecular segments to cooperative motion of molecular microstructure. Accordingly, the conductive network of CNT is partly destroyed, and then some conductive passageways are interrupted. Furthermore, the second electrical conductivity mechanism: electron hopping will be partly limited. Due to the sites' breakage, the distance between CNTs will widen. Then the resistivity will increase distinctly due to its high dependence of electron hopping on the separation distance between CNTs. Thus, the resistivity will start to sharply increase since the peak strain as shown in Fig. 2 (C).